

EFFICIENT OPTIMIZATION OF DETECTION RANGE IN BINARY SENSOR NETWORKS

¹Michael Thomas Greene, ²Lisa Marie Johnson and ³Wei Jun Chen

^{1,2}Department of Electrical Engineering Technology, New York City College of Technology, The City University of New York, 300 Jay St, Brooklyn, NY 11201, USA

³College of Computer Science & Technology, Xi'an University of Science and Technology, 58 Yanta Road, Xi'an 710054, China.

Abstract:

The Internet of Things (IoT) relies on networks of physical objects equipped with sensors and actuators to collect and share data for analysis and decision-making. Wireless sensor networks are fundamental to IoT infrastructure. Binary Sensor Networks, which use simple and cost-effective devices with limited processing capabilities, are increasingly prevalent in IoT applications. They offer advantages over traditional wireless sensor networks by reducing reliance on noisy Received Signal Strength values influenced by environmental factors. Many sophisticated sensors can also function as binary-detection devices by producing binary reports based on predefined thresholds. This binary information is used to determine the presence or absence of a device within a specified area, impacting network coverage, deployment, and accuracy in localization and tracking. This research addresses various problems using binary information, with a focus on IoT applications. It explores the potential of Binary Sensor Networks to improve the efficiency and reliability of IoT systems, especially in situations where complex sensors are not required. The study investigates methods for optimizing coverage, deployment, and positioning accuracy by leveraging binary data, which has practical implications for a wide range of IoT scenarios.

Keywords: Internet of Things (IoT), wireless sensor networks, Binary Sensor Networks, binary information, coverage optimization, deployment, positioning accuracy.

1. Introduction

The Internet of Things (IoT) is comprised of networks of physical objects with embedded sensors and actuators. These objects observe their environment and share the data they collect with each other, internet servers and people. This data is analyzed and the results are used to make decisions and affect changes [1]. Wireless sensor network plays a very important role in the infrastructure of Internet of Things (IoT) [2, 3, 4]. Binary Sensor Networks prevail the traditional Wireless Sensor Network nowadays due to the rationale that large numbers of simple and inexpensive individual devices are expected to be deployed or to be attached to the physical objects for the construction of IoT. These devices require minimal assumptions about sensing capabilities and usually come with limited resources regarding their processing capabilities, memory, and power. It alleviates the requirements of relying on the Received Signal Strength value which is known to be noisy due to the attenuation, reflection and

refraction by the objects and the multi-path interference. Moreover, many sophisticated sensors or devices in traditional wireless sensor networks can also act as binary-detection devices easily by outputting a binary report with predefining a threshold for the measurements [5]. This binary information indicates whether a device is present or absent within a predefined area and the range of

this area directly affect the coverage and the deployment of the network, as well as the positioning accuracy in the widely studied localization and tracking problems. The methodology of a variety of problems using binary information has been addressed by various research groups.

The optimal detection ranges were determined using k-NN algorithm for 1-dimensional, 2-dimensional and 3-dimensional spaces on the principle that node spacing can be derived from the detection range in [7]. These results can be used as the basis for the design of RFID-based positioning systems and other applications. However, they were obtained by minimizing the RMSE for a particular case, that is, when k-NN algorithm was used for localization. Therefore, there is no general conclusion regarding to the optimal detection range.

Optimal arrangements of binary sensors were studied in [8]. The authors aimed to maximize the number of unique distinguishable sub-regions partitioned by the sensing ranges of the sensors. An upper bound on the number of unique subregions is derived to be $n^2 - n + 2$, where n is the number of sensors.

Paper [9] formulated a sensor network position estimation problem as a linear or semidefinite program, which is based on connectivity between nodes. The sensed binary information from the local neighborhood is used to build hop-based virtual distances and it is also suited for low-cost devices. Figure 1 shows a graph of connectivity of a network. The green nodes represent the reference nodes with known positions and the white nodes represent the target nodes with unknown positions. The edge represents the radio link between two nodes indicating that these two nodes are within the communicating range of each other. The objective is to localize the white nodes with the location information of green nodes and the connectivity of the network. Feasible solutions are described to the problem using convex optimization. Additionally, a method for placing rectangular bounds around the possible positions for the unknown nodes is given. However, this method requires centralized computation. Similar work on localization from connectivity can be found in [10].

Fig. 1. Graph of connectivity of a general network.

The APIT (approximate point in time) scheme is presented in [11-12] for range-free localization, which employs an area-based approach to perform localization estimation by isolating the environment into triangular regions between nodes. It is shown that the scheme performs best when an irregular radio pattern and random node placement are considered.

A variety of analytical results were presented in [13] to aid in the design of sensor localization systems based on RSS, quantized RSS, or proximity measurements between sensors. The Cramer-Rao bound is computed to compare the minimal attainable variances of unbiased location estimators for different cases. The results show that lower bounds for standard deviation in proximity-based systems are about 50% higher than the bounds for RSS-based systems. It is also shown that a system with just 3 bits of quantization can be enough in cases.

The remaining of the paper is organized as follows. The mathematical formulation of the optimal detection range problem is presented in Section 2, followed by a numerical method to find the minimum region uncertainty and the simulation results. In Section 3, we formulate the problem by considering two fixed thresholds. We further generalized the problem by allowing different thresholds among sensors in Section 4. The conclusion and future work are provided in Section 5.

2. With Binary Sensing

2.1. Problem formulation

We address a grid network with N by N nodes that are equidistantly located with separation distance equal to d . Let r be the distance that defines the range of the node. For a given r , the area is partitioned into several subregions. We denote the subregions by S_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, I$, with its area being A_i correspondingly, where I is the total number of partitions in this area and A_i represents the uncertainty area when some of the nodes detect the target, which is a function of r . Clearly, if we assume that a target may be anywhere in the area with uniform distribution, the probability that the target is in S_i is given by $p_i = A_i/A$, where $A = [(N-1)d]^2$. We define the expected uncertainty E_u when a target is in the area by

The objective is to find the optimal r that minimizes the expected uncertainty. The

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}u &= \sum_{i=1}^I p_i A_i \\ &= \frac{1}{A} \sum_{i=1}^I A_i^2 = A \sum_{i=1}^I p_i^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\min_r A \sum_{i=1}^I p_i^2 \quad st. \quad \sum_{i=1}^I p_i = 1.$$

problem can be formulated as

The optimal result is obtained when the region is equally partitioned, that is, when all p_i are the same. The resulting optimal E_u is A/I^2 . Since $\lim_{I \rightarrow \infty} A/I^2 = 0$, it is obvious that there's no uncertainty with large enough partitions. However, the region can hardly be equally partitioned due to geometric constraints caused by the sensing nature of the sensors.

2.2. The numeric method

The optimization problem is solved using numeric method by dividing the area into K small grids. For a fixed reading range r , we obtain a set of nodes that can detect the grid k , where $k \in 1, \dots, K$. By counting the number of grids that have the same set (K_j , where $j \in 1, \dots, J$ and J being the total number of different sets), we obtain the probability that the target lies in a certain subregion $p_j = K_j/K$ and hence the corresponding area $A_j = p_j \cdot A$. Therefore, the values of E_u for different r are computed and the minimum E_u and its corresponding r are obtained.

2.3. Simulation results

We consider a grid network with N by N nodes in a region of 10m by 10m. The examples of a 2 by 2 and a

(a) The deployment of a 2 by 2 network. (b) The deployment of a 3 by 3 network.

Fig. 2. The deployment of the grid network in a 10m by 10m region. The yellow circle represents the nodes, the red triangle represents the target and the dashed curve represents the detecting boundary. Figure 3(a) displays E_u as a function of r with different separation distances d . It shows that the smaller d (which means the higher density) achieved smaller E_u . However, smaller separation distance requires more nodes, and thus the system is more expensive, especially when the nodes are the readers and antennas. This is one of the motivations that the binary devices such as proximity sensors are explored to reduce the system cost and meanwhile improve the performance. Figure 3 (b) shows E_u as a function of the ratio r/d . Since larger detecting range requires more energy and is more vulnerable to the noise, we assume that $r \leq 1.5d$, which means that the ratio is constrained to be less than 1.5. The optimal E_u is obtained at $r/d = 0.9$ and the results are shown in Table I. Therefore, people can set the sensing range to be 0.9 of the separation distance for deployment in order to achieve a better localization performance.

(a) E_u vs. detecting range r

(b) E_u vs. ratio r/d

Fig. 3. The expected uncertainty E_u with different separation distances.

3. With Two Fixed Thresholds

3.1. The problem

Here we address the same optimization problem with the same network, but with each node having two thresholds. Denote the two sensing ranges to be r_1 and r_2 and let $r_1 \leq r_2$ without loss of generality. We denote the

expected uncertainty as E_{uu} and our objective is to minimize E_{uu} .

$$\min_{r_1, r_2} A \sum_{i=1}^I p_i (r_1, r_2)^2 \quad \text{st.} \quad \sum_{i=1}^I p_i = 1.$$

3.2. The numeric method

We solve the optimization problem using the same numeric method as that in the previous section by dividing the area into K small grids. To simplify the explanation, we regard the one node with two thresholds as two virtual nodes at the same location but with different sensing ranges. For the fixed reading ranges r_1 and r_2 , we obtain a set of virtual nodes that can detect the grid k , where $k \in 1, \dots, K$. By counting the number of grids that have the same set (K_j , where $j \in 1, \dots, J$ and J being the total number of different sets), we obtain the probability that the target lies in a certain subregion $p_j = K_j/K$ and hence the corresponding area $A_j = p_j \cdot A$. Therefore, we compute the value of E_{uu} for different r_1 and r_2 , and find the minimum E_{uu} and its corresponding r_1 and r_2 .

3.3. Simulation results

We consider a grid network with 2 by 2 nodes in a region of 10m by 10m as shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. The deployment of a 2 by 2 network in a 10m by 10m region. Each node has two sensing ranges. Figure 5 displays E_{uu} as a function of r_1 and r_2 . Figure 5 (a) shows the result in a 2 by 2 network ($d = 10m$) and (b) shows that in a 5 by 5 network ($d = 2.5m$). The smaller d (which means the higher density) achieved smaller E_{uu} . The optimal E_{uu} is obtained at $r_1/d = 0.8$ and $r_2/d = 1$. The results are shown in Table I.

4. With Two Thresholds in Multiple-Stage Case

4.1. The problem

We now consider the case of two thresholds in a sequential way, that is, we suppose at t_1 the sensing range was set to be r_1 and at t_2 the range was set to r_2 . The objective is to find r_2 that minimizes the uncertainty denoted by E_{uu_2} . In other words, the problem is to find an iterative way of choosing ranges so that the target is located as accurately as possible.

4.2. Simulation results

1) Homogenous case: In this case, the nodes are assumed to be homogenous and hence their sensing ranges are the same from each other all the time. We consider a 2 by 2 grid network as an example. Suppose the sensing range of all nodes were fixed at $r_1 = 0.9d$, then the region was divided into several subregions, for instance, 13 subregions as shown in Fig. 1 (a) and 4 different categories because some of the subregions are identical due to symmetry. The area of the subregions and the corresponding detecting sets by the 4 nodes are shown in Table II.

TABLE II THE MINIMUM UNCERTAINTY E_{uu_2}

i	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
A_i	1.1666	1.1666	12.8615	1.1666	12.8615	7.5287	1.1666
Sets	{0, 0, 0, 1}	{0, 0, 1, 0}	{0, 0, 1, 1}	{0, 1, 0, 0}	{0, 1, 0, 1}	{0, 1, 1, 1}	{1, 0, 0, 0}
E_{uu_2min}	0.2950	0.2950	3.7351	0.2950	3.7351	2.1226	0.2950
i	8	9	10	11	12	13	
A_i	12.8615	7.5287	12.8615	7.5287	7.5287	13.7732	
Sets	{1, 0, 1, 0}	{1, 0, 1, 1}	{1, 1, 0, 0}	{1, 1, 0, 1}	{1, 1, 1, 0}	{1, 1, 1, 1}	
E_{uu_2min}	3.7351	2.1226	3.7351	2.1226	2.1226	1.5676	

Figure 6 shows the expected uncertainty E_{uu_2} at time t_2 as a function of r_2 and their minimum values, respectively. We can see that the uncertainty in the region detected by only 1 sensor achieves the minimum value 0.2950 due to the smallest area of the subregion and further division by the second range r_2 . The worst case is in the region detected by two nodes with minimum uncertainty 3.7351, which is still much better than that of the binary case with a minimum value of 10.8354.

2) Heterogeneous case: Different from the previous case, each node can determine its own threshold at every time instant. That is, the sensing range can be different among all nodes. In this case, we might be able to partition the region equally and hence achieves the optimal value $A \sum_{i=1}^I 1/I^2$. For example, in a 2 by 2 grid network,

$$E_{u_{opt}} = 100 \sum_{i=1}^1 31/13^2 = 7.6923.$$

At time t_2 , we can also choose the ranges of the four nodes $r_2^m, m \in \{1,2,3,4\}$ so that each subregion from t_1 can be further partitioned equally.

5. Conclusion and Future Work

This paper investigated the problem of finding the optimal detection range of sensors/devices which generate only binary information indicating whether the target is within its proximity by a predefined detection range in the Internet of Things infrastructure. The binary information is generated by predefining a threshold for the measurements. A method was proposed that determines the optimal detection range by minimizing the region uncertainty. We formulated the optimal detection range problem in three different cases where in the first case, each sensor has only one fixed threshold and in the second case, the binary information was generalized to quantized value with two fixed threshold values. In the third case, the problem was further extended to the cases where the two threshold values can be determined sequentially. For each case, we showed the simulation results using numerical methods to find the minimum region uncertainty. The results show that the proposed method is feasible for achieving an optimal detection range of sensors. Our future work includes to generalize it further to an arbitrary number of thresholds with an analytical solution, to adapt the proposed methods to an irregular network of nodes where everything is done without a central unit, and to apply the results of optimal detection ranges in a practical localization problem.

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